

Mathematical Modeling of Deterministic Systems: Insights from the Tenneti Theory

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Abstract: Pair wise nucleotides¹ modelling act is a significant task in biological systems. This modelling act is crystal clear innovative mathematical act. It is based on attraction between nucleotides, basic arrangement of pattern and logics are taken from nature. Continuous modelling in the pair-wise nucleotides are stable, dynamic, spatial, periodic, auto assemblies, Chaotic and deterministic, it is possible to use both continuous and discrete modelling to interpret microbial behavior. In this version modelling are attached and detached due to thermodynamic attraction force between nucleotides and Chaotic order. It is a good mechanistic modelling act with clear predicting values. It explains various features of system like reverse patterns or biological patterns, modelling act and types of acts, existence and expanding cycles, how 24 micro units (pair wise nucleotides) are generated in the system, separating resulting patterns into groups, relationship with in group and between groups. micro-units, sub units, units, genetic units and pair wise modelling on DNA. How only 5 groups of micro units shall be combining combination and form into genetic code out of 6 groups? This modelling is aims to develop and use efficient algorithms, data structure, visualization communication tools with goal of computer modelling of biological systems. Equating this same modelling system is not possible in theory of probability² in random³ manner. It creates more doubts than answers because theory of probability is not having perfect mathematical logic.

Keywords: RHS Modeling. LHS Modelling. Existence cycle. Existence number, Expanding cycle. Expanding number. Micro unit. Sub unit. Unit. Genetic unit.

I. Introduction

THREE GREAT SCIENTIST THOUGHTS

1) In an article, Erwin Schrödinger⁴ described life as “Genetic code must be in the form of three general statements, (i) the nature of the genetic code is deterministic: (ii) The genetic code is conserved and universal: (iii) The genetic code is oldest known level of complexity in the evolution of living organisms that is accessible to our direct observation and experimental manipulations. In the same article he described “It is an aperiodic crystal. DNA is a crystal, and so is protein, note the pattern. The cleanest view than to the nature of genetic code is that”.

2) In his work Anfinsen^{5,6} described life is “Due to thermodynamic molecular forces, polypeptides automatically assume unique, stable conformed ensembles. This might term the auto-assembly hypothesis of protein synthesis”. And “For every sequence of amino acids there is a unique, defining conformational ensemble to which it must auto assembling”

3) According to Chaos⁷, life is “Chaotic systems appear to be disorder, even random. Beneath the random behavior is sense of order”.

PRESENT SCENARIO - Science works by simplifying complexity, but in the case of genetic code we have over simplified it.

In fact, we still do not understand nature’s nifty crystal-forming algorithms affectionately referred to as the genetic code. Codons⁸ are permutations of three nucleic acids. They have a specific configuration of set, which in this case has three members. Permutations are actual arrangements of symbols. For instance, the sequence of symbols XYZ is a

permutation of the symbols X, Y and Z. other permutation of the same symbols are YZX, or ZYX, Taking the number of possible symbols, in this case 4 nucleic acids, and raising it to a power of the number of symbols in the permutation, in this case 3, determine the total set of permutations. Therefore, there are sixty-four ($4^3=4*4*4=64$). It is a fact that twenty amino acid set is standard set.

Using 64 codons to only assigned 20 amino acids is wasteful information. In this system, we are missing something?

Evaluating biological acts through theory of probability in a random manner create more doubts than answers. Because what kind of mechanism follows inside mother womb we don’t know. In the same manner what type of arrangement act take lead role and other parameters like attraction forces in between nucleotides we did not understand. So present mathematical theory of probability cannot solve the problem. It creates puzzles in the mind.

Let us take four pairs of nucleotides the bases adenine (A), cytosine (C), guanine (G), and thymine (T) are as a blocks with four different colors. Black border with black letters blocks are belongs to egg group and red border blocks with red letters are belongs to mate group. This is case study for the type of arrangement and the role of attraction. They can arrange in three types. Reverse order (Figure-1A). Parallel order (Figure-1B). Random order (Figure-1C).

PAIR WISE NUCLEOTIDES MODELING ACT WITH RESPECT TO TYPE OF PATTERN & NUCLEOTIDES ATTRACTION FORCES:

Let us take four pairs of nucleotide the bases adenine (A),

cytosine (C), guanine (G), and thymine (T) are as a blocks with four different colors. Black border with black letters blocks are belongs to egg group and red border blocks with red letters are belongs to mate group. This is case study for the type of arrangement and the role of attraction. They can arrange in three types. Reverse order (Figure-1A). Parallel order (Figure-1B). Random order (Figure-1C).

3.1 Figures and Tables

Place illustrations (figures, tables, drawings, and Taking concept attraction bond in between homologous nucleotides. Fig -2A, 2B and 2C explains about relation between pattern and attraction between homologous nucleotides. In reverse order, attraction lines pass through center point in X-Y plane, it have chance of nucleotides momentum in a balance manner. In parallel order attraction lines are in parallel, and in the random order attraction lines are in zigzag way. illustration numbers and caption under the illustration in 10 pt font. Do not allow illustrations to extend into the margins or the gap between columns (except 2-column illustrations may cross the gap). If your figure has two parts, include the labels "(a)" and "(b)".

Fig-3A explain further actions of homologous nucleotides in reverse order, attraction forces pass through center point, based on these forces the modelling of nucleotides form X shape. In parallel order (Fig-3B) homologous nucleotides are *INTRODUCING FOUR PAIRS NUCLEOTIDES MATHEMATICAL MODELLING ACT.*

Four pairs of nucleotides mean eight elements, they generate factorial 8 number of sequences, that is equal to 40320.

Separating patterns into groups is a new innovate thinking. The most abstract level in this hierarchy is the mathematical model. Here the behavior of a system is reproduced as a series of mathematical relationships which reflect and often predict its behavior. This is the required basic input data to separate the system in the Hamiltonian path of elements modeling and ends are free, which explains modeling act in mathematical determinism in polynomial time 10,11,12 mathematical logics.

II. Theory

THREE TYPES OF MATHEMATICS TO UNDERSTAND BIOLOGICAL ACTS.

1) Class-1 involves routine application of existing mathematical techniques to solve biological problem, for example mitosis cell division the cell division can explain in term of multiplying by using present mathematics.

2) Class-2 some fundamental issues in biology required all together new way of thinking quantitatively or analytically.

Creation of entirely new area of mathematics may be necessary before it will be possible to grapple successfully with the underlying biological problems. Examples are events in fertilization like egg selecting matured sperm, chromosomes cross-over, tree of life --- nucleotides arrangement on DNA.

3) Class-3, Third class is combining of known and un-known it is combining of mitosis and meiosis.

MODELLING ACT The modelling act is look like Riffle shuffling act but it fallows certain rules and regulations where shuffling act is in random. A common shuffling technique is called the riffle or dovetail shuffle, in which half of the deck is held in each hand with the thumb inward, then cards are released by the thumb so that they fall to the table interleaved. The Gilbert-Shannon-Reeds model provides a mathematical model of the random outcomes. Riffle shuffling is in between two groups.

KEY WORDS: RHS Modeling. LHS Modelling. Existence cycle. Existence number, Expanding cycle. Expanding number.

Micro unit. Sub unit. Unit. Genetic unit.

MODELLING ACT: A key function of the model therefore is to predict behavior. A model is only validated if such predictions are confirmed. Modeling is arrangement elements of two groups (four pairs) like Hamiltonian path in ascending manner. "Hamiltonian path is a traceable path is a path visit each nearest group vertex element exactly once in ascending manner". Reverse order taken for the experiment.

RULE-1 Modelling act is in between two groups of elements; each group must have equal numbers of elements. In a group each one of the nucleotide is one of homologous nucleotide. So number of elements are equal to $2N$ (N - indicate elements in each group) . in the case of three groups then total elements are $3N$ --- like wise.

RULE-2 This rule explains combining of both group elements are based on "first come first serve principle". Modelling act in between two groups are as follows. Take first nucleotide of 1st group as 1st position. Second group 1st nucleotide occupies 2nd position. First group 2nd nucleotide as 3rd position. Second group 2nd nucleotide as 4th position, --- like wise first group last nucleotide is $(2N-1)$ th position, and 2nd group last nucleotide as last or $2N$ th position in combined group.

RULE-3 This rule explains separating of combined element group into two groups, in this process separating first half or four nucleotides as first group and second four nucleotides as second group, that result re-constitute pattern. In the case of more than two groups same rule applies with respect to

number of groups. This modelling act is two types RHS modelling act and LHS modelling act.

RHS MODELLING ACT Taking right hand side group as first- and left-hand side group as second and follow the rules of modelling are mention above and carry out the modelling process is known as RHS modelling act.

LHS MODELLING ACT Taking left hand side group as first and right hand side group as second and follow the rules of

RIGHT HAND SIDE MODELLING ACT

LEFT HAND SIDE MODELLING ACT

OBSERVATIONS

- 1) The process of system follows Hamiltonian path in both RHS and LHS modelling.
- 2) The system can predicable in easy manner.
- 3) First group first nucleotide and second group last nucleotide not change their original place; remain nucleotides changes their original places in RHS modelling act.
- 4) Second group first nucleotide and first group last nucleotide not change their original place; remain nucleotides changes their original places in LHS modelling act.

EXISTENCE CYCLE & EXISTENCE NUMBER.

The system is developed on the basis of nature rules and regulations so it is very important to understand complete system and system features.

RHS PAIR WISE NUCLEOTIDES AUTO MODELLING ACT FOR EXISTENCE.

LHS PAIR WISE NUCLEOTIDES AUTO MODELLING ACT FOR EXISTENCE.

For that repeating modelling act on resulting patterns is in both methods is very important. Repeating act on resulting reconstitute patterns till to the pattern became original or existence, this cycle of act known as Existence cycle. nucleotides auto arrangement acts are periodic or existence.

OBSERVATIONS:

- 1) Either RHS or LHS arrangement or modelling, both systems are periodic auto-assemblies and system are predictable, where it is not possible in random shuffling.
- 2) In RHS modelling first group first nucleotide and second group last nucleotide never change its position.
- 3) In LHS modelling second group first nucleotide and first group last nucleotide never change its position.
- 4) Either RHS or LHS modelling, both systems are existence after three iterations.
- 5) The difference is resulting reconstitute patterns are different compare RHS modelling with LHS modelling.
- 6) Modelling of existing cycle is also applicable to parallel and random patterns.
- 7) With respect to four pair nucleotides they also periodic auto segments and results reconstitute pattern are different with respect RHS and LHS modelling.

SELECTING NATURES BIOLOGICAL PATTERN OR MICRO UNITS-

Taking four pairs of nucleotide as a micro-unit, how the nature micro-unit structure is play key role in genetic code? It is very important to the system because the overall code is combinations of twenty-four micro units. The micro-unit pattern can define in three existence cycle which are given below.

- 1) The first one is reverse modelling micro-unit where RHS group nucleotides modelling is reverse to LHS group nucleotides modelling.
- 2) The second one is parallel modelling micro-unit where RHS group nucleotides modelling is parallel to LHS group nucleotides modelling.
- 3) The third one is random modelling micro-unit where RHS group nucleotides modelling is random to LHS group nucleotides modelling.

The most important part is which type of pattern modelling have a capacity to carry out a perfect genetic code. It is also important weather genetic code is developing with three nucleotides (as per present science) or some other modelling. But is true that four pair nucleotide arrangement or modelling on DNA calling as genetic code. In this case four pairs of nucleotides are taken as micro-unit in the system. It is smallest unit in genetic code. It is very important to understand micro-units, types of micro-units with respect to both end nucleotides, separating them into groups, examine them how they bond each other with in the group and selecting suitable possibility for bonding as sub units. How sub units further develop into group units. How group units are bond with other group units. All these home work is very important to understand how four pairs nucleotide modelling DNA.

OBSERVATIONS; - The following observations are very important to study and understand features of micro-unit expansion cycles. From all three cycles (reverse existence cycle, parallel existence cycle and random existence cycle) which system is perfectly match for biological acts.

- 1) Incisional stage reverses order micro-unit, parallel order micro-unit and random order micro-unit their sequence of nucleotides are as per definition of pattern but one thing is common the is each group have four nucleotides, each one of nucleotide is one of the homologous nucleotides,
- 2) In the reverse micro unit, the attraction in between homologous nucleotides are in X-shape formation throughout the periodic cycle. That means the reverse system follows same type modelling order in generated reconstitute micro-units. The modelling order is in such way each group have four nucleotides, each nucleotide is one of the homologous nucleotide.
- 3) In the case of parallel order, the result reconstitute micro-unit are not follow parallel order arrangement. However homologous nucleotides are mixing up in each group. So no chances of parallel attraction in between homologous nucleotides.
- 4) In the case of random order, the result reconstitute micro-unit are follow random order arrangement. However homologous nucleotides are not mixing up in each group. Random attraction in between homologous nucleotides.

Parallel order and random order micro-unit's existence cycles very clearly explains these micro-units modelling are not suitable for biological act. But with respect to reverse order it have special feature let study, understand, analyzing and compare the basic conditions are required for biological acts.

- 1) In entire existence cycle in reverse order, reconstitute micro-units follow a systematic balancing, they are crystal clear to understanding each micro-unit structural formation or result modelling.
- 2) With homologous nucleotides attraction in micro-unit can create perfect equilibrium momentum in the systems. Homologous nucleotides attraction is in diagonal. No chance of homologous nucleotides combined together.

3) Nature designs the system in such beautiful balance way, the system is perfectly static in normal condition. The code of micro-unit is unique and universal, same code can follow to all creatures.

4) Diagonal attraction in between homologous nucleotides effect is easy to separate and easy to mutually interchange in biological acts.

5) The combinations of micro-unit nucleotide arrangements and attraction in between homologous nucleotides create nature's acts; those are auto sequences or auto micro-unit codes.

6) The folding capabilities are more in the system. It leads more compressive and easier to enlarge because diagonal attraction creates spiral way of formation in the system it is actual DNA shape. In the shape creates compressive ness due the same attraction in between them.

7) In the case of biological act crossing over the attraction with in the micro-unit transform to attract mate micro-unit.

8) At this stage the compressed chromosome enlarge and one strand separate from the system were same strand present in mate non-sister chromosome.

9) Crossing-over is in between one set of homologous chromosomes and 22 pairs of non-sister chromosomes. So homologous chromosomes have same genetic code throughout its length. Such a situation both chromosomes are enlarged and mutually inter change one strand from each. This modelling has all biological reasons to perform biological acts.

EXPANDING CYCLE & EXPANDING NUMBER,

Once the system is parodic or existence further modelling or further iteration has no use, the system keeps or repeating in both RHS & LHS modeling. To understand the system, resulting reconstitute patterns of RHS modeling cycle further carry out LHS modelling operation. In the same manner resulting reconstitute pattern of LHS modelling further carry out RHS modeling operation. In this situation the system generates more existing cycles. This is known as system expanding, it is better way to understand expanding cycle. Expanding cycle is defined as "Pool of reconstitute patterns are in a combination of number of existence cycles generate through alternative combination of RHS modeling and LHS modelling". This expanding cycle is mathematically explainable and equitable.

- 1) Suppose a pattern goes under RHS modelling and generate X-number of reconstitute pattern in a first generation, equal to (E_n-1) .
- 2) (E_n-1) number of patterns further goes under LHS Modelling and generate $(E_n-1)^2$ number of reconstitute patterns in second generation.
- 3) $(E_n-1)^2$ number of patterns further goes under RHS modelling and generate $(E_n-1)^3$ number of reconstitute patterns in third generation--- likewise the system keeps on expanding.
- 4) After some generations reconstitute pattern and existence cycles are keeps on repeating in both modellings. So further expanding is not having any logic.
- 5) The number of reconstitute patterns are in the system is more important.
- 6) The total number of reconstitute patterns in the system is known as expanding number.

$$\text{The system equitation} = 1 + (E_n-1) + (E_n-1)^2 + (E_n-1)^3$$

From ancient society to modern silicon society our mathematical logic is polynomial, it is based on mathematical verbs adding (+), subtraction (-), multiplication (x) and dividing (/). Apart from present mathematical verbs, there are other mathematical

acts are present in nature like modeling. The modeling act is not shuffling¹¹ act in random¹² manner. Because random systems are not predicting next patterns, systems existence and total patterns (Factorial N) separating them into groups. In this situation the system creates more doubts than answers, feeding random logic to the computer create computational complexity¹³.

Micro-units expanding cycles explains how the system works in defined deterministic manner. The cells generation in stage by stage is follows same method in the chromosomes crossing-over act in a large scale, because the number of chromosomes in human cell equal to 23 pairs. The expanding number in human chromosomes expanding cycle is equal to cells present in human body. To develop such a bigger human chromosome expanding cycle further needs a group research with biologists and software developers to development of suitable software.

FIRST PAIR WISE NUCLEOTIDES EXPANDING CYCLE.

This expanding cycle is combination of 15 existence cycles. in the expanding cycle only 12 patterns are generating (X1, X2,X3---X12). Further expanding, system repeats same patterns. System expanding number is 12. All sequence in the systems are in reverse order.

Figure-7A

SECOND PAIR WISE NUCLEOTIDES EXPANDING CYCLE.

The system is combination of 15 existence cycles. Only 12 patterns are generating in the system (Y1, Y2, Y3---Y12). Further expanding results same patterns are repeats. Each

pattern in the system follows a one basic principle, which is reverse order.

Figure-7B

RECONSTITUTE PATTERNS FROM EXPANDING CYCLE-1

Figure-8A

RECONSTITUTE PATTERNS FROM EXPANDING CYCLE-2

Figure-8B

WHY SYSTEM NEED TWO EXPANDING CYCLES

The answer is the following reasons.

- 1) Twelve reconstitute patterns are not sufficient to explain biological act, assume nature working with two expanding cycles.
- 2) In a reverse order keeping one group completely egg nucleotides another as sperm nucleotides, system can format in 24 combinations but all combinations result only 24 patterns.

BINARY HEAP

Pattern expanding in the system is like a binary heap, each pattern has at most two children. Which are referred as the right child and left child. A recursive definition using just set theory notions is that a binary tree is a triple (R. S. L), where R is RHA act result reconstitute sequences (in black branches), L is LHA act result reconstitute sequences (in red branches), S is a singleton set's original pattern. It is mostly similar like binary heap; it is complete binary tree that is in all levels of the tree, the level is mathematical mention as iteration. In the case of binary heap except possibly the last one (deepest) fully filled and last level of the tree is not complete. But in this case of expanding cycle, expanding cycle is combination of existence cycles, existence cycles are endless so last level of tree is complete, and all nodes are equal. In the binary heap only 12 sequences are keep on repeating, those mention in dotted boundaries.

PATTERN EXPANDING SYSTEM IN THE FORM OF BINARY HEAP.

Figure-9

HAMILTONIAN CYCLE

Hamiltonian circuit, vertex tour or graph cycle is cycle that visits each vertex exactly once (except for the vertex that is both the start and end, which is visited twice). In the arrangement act sequence or reconstitute patterns are developing one after another in periodic formats. In the above figure-9 capital A, B, C---L represent to P1, P2, P3---P12 because of space constrains. Black circles or cycles are representing to RHA act and yellow circles or cycles are representing to LHA act, and arrows directions represent to the way of reconstitute patterns are generating. Sequences are developing in the form of Hamiltonian path or cycles sequences are traced in a single direction, the vertices are connected with arrows and the edges traced "tail -to -head, it is proof for Hamiltonian cycles.

PATTERN EXPANDING CYCLE IN THE FORM OF HAMILTONIAN CYCLE.

Figure-10

Polynomial-time equations; - A mathematical expression that involves N's and N² s and N's raised to other powers is called a polynomial-time, and that's what the "P" in "P = NP" stands for. P is the set of problems whose solution times are proportional to polynomials involving N's. NP-class problems include many pattern-matching and optimization problems that are of great practical interest, such as determining the optimal arrangement of transistors on a silicon chip, developing accurate financial-forecasting models, or analyzing protein-folding behavior in a cell.

All patterns are not possible to equate, there are some series of patterns are only possible to equate, which are based on relationship in between the series. The relationship is with respect to columns and rows.

Equation-1: For example Columns are P and rows are Q, which is equal to P, or columns and rows are equal (P=T1 and Q=T1), then existence number= 1+1=2, that means after 2nd iteration the system become original.

Equation-2: The relation between columns and rows are mathematically express that involves to the raised to powers with both columns and rows bases are equal, those series are equitable. For better understanding; A pattern has Tn columns and Tm rows (columns, P=Tn and rows=Q=Tm), then the existence number equal to combining of to the power= (n+m), that means the system existence after (n + m) iterations. Columns P= Tn, Rows Q=Tm then Existence number of the order= (n + m)

Equation for expanding no. for equitable series = Existence number *Number of elements in order/2, (Note - This equation is just imagination based on 2 columns and 4 rows this equation is to further equate perfectly).

NECESSARY CONDITIONS FOR PAIR WISE NUCLEOTIDE MODELLING ON DNA

Fertilization is a natural event; the role of man and woman is up to sex only. Later what is happening inside mother womb no one don't know. We are assuming and praying for good results. Even doctor's biologist knows only symptoms. Nature's events are not based on freewill or random. Nature's selection is only determined. This nature's determinism is part of every micro-unit, sub units, units, genetic units, chromosomes, cells, cells generation to zygote. Mother womb has perfect determined mathematical chain of events, which are developing output in fixed time. For this determinism has necessary conditions.

- 1) Nature's genetic code must be deterministic; it must be conserved and universal.
- 2) Genetic code an aperiodic crystal, the combination of code and thermodynamic molecular forces developing unique, stable conformed ensembles.
- 3) For every sequence of amino acids there is a unique, defining conformational ensemble to which it must auto assembling.
- 4) The code shall be static, dynamic, spatial, symmetric, most compressed, enlargeable and easy to mutually inter changeable.

On the basis of system requirement to further formulate pairwise arrangement on DNA. Separating both expanding cycles into groups based on end nucleotides. It is very important to understand each group; they can combine together to form into genetic code. How many groups can combine all these are important questions?

DEFINITION MICRO-UNIT; - Micro unit is nothing but a pattern or reconstitute pattern, each pattern has two groups, each group have four nucleotides, each nucleotide in any one group is one of the homologous nucleotide. The nucleotide arrangement sequence in reverse order. That mean any one of the group nucleotides arrangement sequence is reverse to other group nucleotides sequence. Total micro units are 24. Length of each micro unit is four letters.

MICRO UNITS MODELLING; -The process of lining up any one of group micro units to achieves maximum level of identity and conservation for nucleotides sequences for the purpose of assessing degree of similarity and the possibility of homology. In any case pair wise nucleotides pattern never change.

Figure-11,

The above figure explains four pair wise nucleotides modelling patterns further separates into six groups based on patterns both end nucleotides.

- 1) Micro Units X1, X8, Y2 & Y11 are 1st group.
- 2) Micro Units X2, X11, Y1 & Y8 are 2nd group.
- 3) Micro Units X3, X10, Y3 & Y10 are 3rd group.
- 4) Micro Units X4, X12, Y4 & Y12 are 4th group.
- 5) Micro Units X5, X6, Y9, & Y7 are 5th group.
- 6) Micro Units X7, X9, Y5 & Y6 are 6th group.

EXAMINE MICRO UNITS' NUCLEOTIDES BONDING WITH IN GROUP.

DEFINITION OF SUB UNIT - Combining combination of micro units within the group with respect to nucleotide attraction forces, which are suitable to conditions like static, dynamic, spatial, symmetric, most compressed, enlargeable and easy to mutually inter changeable.

For this experiment group-1 micro units are taken as samples. All results combinations are not suitable for sub units as definition. Out of all combinations some of them are suitable. The goal is select to some of them.

parentheses.

Figure: -12

- 1) micro units four are developing six combinations which are shown above.
- 2) Out of six combinations two or 1/3 combinations are 100% parallel attraction bond in between micro units.
- 3) Another two combinations or 1/3 combinations are 1/3% diagonal attraction and 2/3% are parallel attraction in between micro units.
- 4) Remain two combinations or 1/3 combinations are 2/3% diagonal attraction and 1/3% are parallel attraction in between micro units.

CASE STUDY BASED ON BIOLOGICAL CONDITIONS ARE REQUIRED

- 1) In this innovative work, the system is deterministic, universal, aperiodic crystal where all possibilities are follows.
- 2) Parallel attraction in between reconstitute patterns are more suitable for biological act because one is the system is more static, and gene length will be longer, easy to separate,

and can be equated in computer system. Earth is revolving around the Sun results the seasons like summer, spring, rainy, and winter. All seasons come one after another in periodic manner; this is one mega cycle in a year. With respect to the mega cycle, billions of creatures start their life cycle on Mother Earth. Re-production is the main events in a creature's life to generate their off springs. In this process two gametes generate required number of cells for creatures' zygote. This is nature's modelling act in between two sets of chromosomes. It is possible to nature act to generate perfect genetic sequences. but computers cannot evaluate system because present mathematics are not suitable.

Fertilization is un-broken chains of events from egg selection to offspring in the interval of 9 months an average; it is similar like a modern car manufacture company where each car comes out of the factory in the interval of one hour. For this process every operation in all mega systems to micro-systems have time frame, very well defined and in perfect mathematical model. Any small mistake in any one of system cannot give planned results. This system cannot possible to think in the random order. Similar-way each micro-biological act to mega-act is in perfect mathematical model. Nature modelling act is based on chromosomes attraction forces and reverse of chromosomes. These modelling must be static, dynamic determined, spatial, symmetric, most compressed, enlargeable, and easy to mutually inter-changeable.

ANSWERS FOR UN SOLVED QUESTIONS IN SCIENCE AS PER NATURE'S DETERMINISM THEORY IN MICRO BIOLOGY

- 1) How egg attract matured sperm.
- 2) Gametes further develops reconstitute cells.
- 3) Chromosomes cross-over.
- 4) Cells generation in the combination of meiosis and mitosis.
- 5) Twin tree of life.
- 6) How the resulting off-springs as a boy or girl or hermaphrodite in perfect fertilization.
- 7) Fertilization and natural problems.
- 8) Due to natural problems results fertilization as twins, twins as boys, twins as a girl, twins as boy and girl but not hermaphrodites.
- 9) Combined twins and more twins.

References

- [1].A. Van Zuylen and F. Schalekamp, "The Achilles' Heel of the GSR Shuffling: A Note on New Age Solitaire," *Probability in the Engineering and Informational Sciences*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 315–328, 2004, doi: 10.1017/S0269964804183034.
- [2].D. J. Bennett, *Randomness*, Harvard University Press, 1998, ISBN: 0-674-10745-4.
- [3].E. Schrödinger, "What is Life?; The Physical Aspect of Living Cell," lectures delivered at Trinity College, Dublin, under the auspices of the Dublin Institute for Advanced Studies, Feb. 1943, 1944.
- [4].*Christian Anfinsen Papers (1939-1999)*, National Library of Medicine finding aid.
- [5].*The Christian B. Anfinsen Papers*, Profiles in Science, National Library of Medicine.
- [6]. "Chaos theory," accessed from http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chaos_theory.

[7]. "Amino Acid and Codons Table," CBS, available at: <http://www.cbs.dtu.dk/course/27619/codon.html>.

[8].W. R. Hamilton, "Account of the Icosian Calculus," *Proceedings of the Royal Irish Academy*, vol. 6, pp. 415–416, 1858.

[9].M. Sipser, *Introduction to the Theory of Computation*, Course Technology Inc., 2006, ISBN: 0-619-21764-2.

[10].C. H. Papadimitriou, *Computational Complexity*, Addison-Wesley, 1994, ISBN: 0-201-53082-1.

[11].A. Cobham, "The intrinsic computational difficulty of functions," *Proc. Logic, Methodology, and Philosophy of Science II*, North Holland, 1965.

[12].P. Diaconis, *Group Representation in Probability and Statistics* (Lecture Notes), 1988.

[13].A. Nakabachi et al., "Endosymbiotic genome reduction in *Buchnera* and other bacteria," *Science*, vol. 314, p. 267, 2006; V. Pérez-Brocail et al., *Science*, vol. 314, pp. 312–313, 2006; A. C. Forster et al., "Construction of synthetic life forms," *Nature Molecular Systems Biology*, vol. 2, 2006, doi: 10.1038/msb4100090.

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Tenneti Vijay Kumar received his B.E. degree in Mechanical Engineering from Andhra University, Visakhapatnam, in 1981. He worked as a mechanical engineer in various national and international companies, gaining over four decades of professional experience. Since 1982, he has dedicated himself to developing the Tenneti Theory of Determinism, a novel mathematical framework inspired by shuffling rules and deterministic systems. His work explores applications in computer complexity, P vs NP problems, anti-piracy solutions, and innovative technologies. In 2011, he authored *Tenneti Theory of Determinism*, providing insights into mathematical patterns in fertilization and deterministic processes. Despite lacking formal degrees in related sciences, he continues to seek collaboration to contribute his findings to global research.